

EXPERIMENTAL DETERMINATION OF STRAIN INHOMOGENEITIES IN WOVEN LAMINATES BY FBG

A.Güemes, A. Fernandez-Lopez, C. Dominguez, C. de Miguel
Dpt. Aeronautics, Univ Politecnica Madrid, Spain
Plaza Cardenal Cisneros, 3 MADRID E-28040
Alfredo.guemes@upm.es

SUMMARY

FBGs bonded on the surface of a woven laminate will experience a strong spectral distortion under loads, due to local strain changes at the tows coming from the warp or weft directions. The interest of the work is two-fold. On one side, it is useful to obtain the mesoscale strain field, and may be used to validate the meso-FE models, which have received a great attention to predict the strength and stiffness of textile composites. On the other hand, it point out the importance of shielding the sensor when embedded into fabric composites, to get meaningful results. The results are compared to those recently obtained by other authors with a different technique.

Keywords: Structural Health Monitoring, Fibre optic sensors, strain measurement, fabrics. modelling strain woven composites meso-scale

INTRODUCTION

Fibre optic sensors of the kind of Bragg grating are increasingly being used for strain monitoring, either embedded in composite laminates, or bonded onto the surface. Normally a single peak is expected, and commercial interrogation systems only looks for peak wavelength drifting. Sometimes, looking at the reflection spectrum, a more complex spectrum appears, due to strong strain gradients along the FBG.

Many authors have predicted these local strain changes in textile composites; a large review has been recently published (ref 1), the local strain field was experimentally obtained by digital image correlation techniques.

Many authors have experiences the difficulties of embedding fibre optic sensors inside composites done with fabrics, and cured at high pressure, needed to obtain a good quality composite. Two phenomena are usually happening; a strong signal attenuation, due to microbending of the optical fibre; and a strong signal distortion, which made impossible to identify a single peak, even in the unloaded structure. A common practice to avoid these problems is to include the optical fibre inside an aligned tape, then proceed to the curing process.

This work is related not to embedded fibres, but to optical fibres sensors bonded at the surface of an already cured textile composite. Still, the local strain inhomogeneities will distort the spectrum when loading the structure, as has been experimentally obtained.

EXPERIMENTAL MATERIALS AND METHODS

These experiments were done inside a project related to get information about the internal strain field created during a bonded repair, by a stepped joint (figure 1). Parent laminate was a quasiisotropic 3 mm thick graphite/epoxy laminate AS4/8552, done with fabric prepreps, and cured under a conventional cycle in autoclave.

Figure 1. Sketch of the composite step bonded joint, and FBG sensors distribution

Then the steps were sanded, according to the Airbus SRM, and a optical fibre with 5 engraved FBG was carefully located onto the adhesive film, and new fresh prepreg layers were put to reconstruct the laminate, and cured at the nominal temperature, but under reduced pressure. Specimens for tensile tests 15 mm wide were prepared, and tested with a MTS 810. Load was increased by 1 kN steps, the spectrum was acquired at each step. Specimens failure happened at 13,15 kN (average of 5 specimens), but data acquisition from the FBGs were lost at 6-7 kN, because of fibre breaks.

The optical interrogation system was a Micron Optics SI 720. Five gratings, 10 mm length and without recoating, were adequately spaced in frequency to avoid any overlapping (figure 2)

Figure 2. Spectrum of the optical fibre with the 5 FBGs, before embedding

As expected, the spectrum of the embedded gratings distorted when loading, due to the complex stress field; they also suffers from strong attenuation, caused by the height of the steps, comparable to the fibre diameter. But also the FBG 1, which was bonded on a flat surface, sowed two peaks when loading, the explanation is given next.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Figure 3 shows the spectrum of the 10 mm surface bonded grating, under different load increments (1 kN cause a peak drifting about 600 pm, or nearly 500 microstrains). Instead of using the normal scaling, the Y-axis of the spectrum is given in dB, to get higher visibility on the changes. The trend is quite clear, the single peak for the unloaded grating is changing to two or more peaks, whose distance is also increasing among them.

Figure 3. Spectrum of a long FBG bonded at the surface of a textile composite, under uniaxial load

To clarify the phenomenon, the following experiment was prepared: New short FBGs, 2 mm long, were engraved, and carefully bonded on the laminate surface, at warp or weft position of the fabric, as shown in figure 4.

Figure 4 Position of the FBGs in the laminate

OPTICAL SPECTRUM OBTAINED WITH THE SHORTER GRATINGS

The next figure shows the evolution of the spectrum of the FBG 1, under increasing load. The peak drifting is clearly seen, without any distortion. Near identical results were obtained with the FBG 2, located in a similar position.

At 7 KN, the corresponding strain were 3348,04732 $\mu\epsilon$ and 3264,28515 $\mu\epsilon$, and the linearity load.VS.strain was near perfect, as seen at figure 7.

Fig.5. Spectrum of a 2 mm FBG, bonded at a warp position.

A similar peak shape, but with higher strains values (about 10 %) , were obtained with FBG 3 (FBG4 was disbonded, its results are discarded). Comparative results are given at the Table 1.

	1 KN	9 KN
RED 1	376,523175 $\mu\epsilon$	3663,57863 $\mu\epsilon$
RED 2	373,270275 $\mu\epsilon$	3697,73408 $\mu\epsilon$
RED 3	437,51505 $\mu\epsilon$	4117,35818 $\mu\epsilon$

DISCUSSION

The next figure shows the spectrum of the FBG 5, which is partially bonded on the warp region, and partially bonded on the weft region, experiencing different strain level, and consequently, showing wavelength drifting at this two levels. FBGs do not behave as local averaging sensors, as the electrical strain gauges do, but they are really distributed sensors. A comparison of peak drifting is given at Figure 7. Strains obtained with the long gratings are apparently higher than those obtained with shorter gratings, due to the fact that only peak value at the spectrum is considered in the calculations. This anomaly could be explained by the fact that shorter gratings have wider peaks

Figure 6. Spectrum of a long 10 mm FBG, bonded on a textile composite

Figure 7. Strains .VS. Load obtained with the different FBGs

CONCLUSIONS

The texture of the fabric in a textile composite will promote significant differences in the strain field, and it will be reflected at the spectrum of a grating bonded to the laminate. This phenomenon has to be considered when using FBG with fabric composites; particularly with embedded sensors, the strain field can be so strongly distorted that strain readings would be quite inaccurate.

For surface bonded sensors, it allows for a local measurements of the strains, affording a new technique for validation of the mesophase models of fabric composites.

References

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